

BEYOND ACCESS: EXPLORING ACCESSIBILITY, CHALLENGES, AND PERCEPTIONS OF HEALTHCARE AMONG SENIOR CITIZENS IN PAYATAS, QUEZON CITY

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ABSTRACT

Republic Act No. 9994, the Expanded Senior Citizen Act of 2010 in the Philippines, enhances benefits for those aged 60 and above, acknowledging their societal contributions. It offers increased discounts on medical services and goods, tax exemptions, and priority access to government services, such as basic healthcare services. This qualitative study focuses on the experiences of ten (10) senior citizen participants, five (5) males and five (5) females aged 60 and above, accessed through purposive sampling. Data were collected via semi-structured, open-ended interviews conducted during monthly senior citizens' events and home visits. The interviews, conducted in English and Filipino, were analyzed through coding and thematizing to organize coherent themes. Findings reveal significant gaps in awareness among senior citizens regarding barangay-specific healthcare programs and services. Identified barriers include physical distance to health facilities, inconsistent service availability, and prolonged waiting times. Participants suggest personalized care, better service access, and expanded outreach programs. While some senior citizens commend the healthcare center's efficiency and quality, others express dissatisfaction with wait times, staff approachability, and medication availability. The study underscores the critical role of barangay health centers in senior citizen healthcare access and the necessity for improved communication and service enhancements in local healthcare systems. Identifying key barriers and perceptions highlights the need for targeted interventions to improve service delivery, staff training, and medication availability. Implementing these recommendations could significantly enhance healthcare experiences for seniors,

promoting their health, fulfillment, and overall well-being, thus aligning with the objectives of the Expanded Senior Citizen Act of 2010.

Keywords: *Perception, Barriers, Senior citizen, Elderly, Healthcare Center, Qualitative research*

INTRODUCTION

As the global population ages, the healthcare needs of senior citizens become increasingly vital. According to the World Health Organization (2022), the reported rise in the global aging population is taking place, and the consequences of this demographic shift are only now being comprehended at both the national and international levels. This transformation has widespread implications across various sectors of society, influencing the need for commodities and services like housing, transportation, and social welfare. Additionally, it affects family dynamics, intergenerational connections, and labor and financial markets (Dugarova, 2016). This demographic shift is particularly evident in countries like Japan and Singapore, where the proportion of elderly individuals exceeds that of younger demographics, presenting unique challenges regarding healthcare, social services, and economic sustainability (Apolitical, 2020).

In the Philippines, like many other nations, addressing the health and well-being of the elderly has emerged as a prominent concern, especially in one of the largest and most populous barangays in the nation, Quezon City. Grappling with the challenges of ensuring adequate healthcare access and services for its retired senior citizens, the success of health center programs in this bustling urban community can be measured beyond mere accessibility; it must encompass the active engagement and participation of retired senior citizens as a central metric.

Attitudes toward aging and senior citizens exhibit substantial variation across different cultures and geographic regions. While some societies deeply respect their elders, valuing them as repositories of wisdom and experience, others marginalize or underestimate their contributions. As senior citizens grow older, they encounter various difficulties, such as societal stigmatization and prevalent negative attitudes, often found in contexts portrayed in the media (Edström, 2018). Familial generational dynamics and broader socioeconomic and political factors profoundly influence these perceptions.

The term "senior citizen" in the Philippines refers to individuals 60 years old and above. This definition stems from Republic Act No. 9994, commonly referred to as the "Expanded Senior Citizens Act of 2010," enacted on February 15, 2010. Under this law, senior citizens are entitled to various privileges and benefits, including discounts on goods and services, access to social services and healthcare, and other incentives to improve their quality of life and well-being (Republic of the Philippines, 2010).

The research aims to delve deeply into these programs, uncovering their intricate aspects and assessing their impact on the well-being of the senior population. It seeks to shed light on both the challenges faced by senior citizens and the healthcare providers

responsible for these initiatives. Furthermore, this research explores innovative strategies and interventions that could enhance senior citizens' active participation in healthcare center programs. With a strong commitment to improving the senior healthcare experience, the study aspires to be a source of knowledge and a driver of positive change in how healthcare centers serve and support this population group.

Research Questions

The aging population poses both a challenge and an opportunity for healthcare centers. Customized programs for seniors are crucial, yet there's a gap in understanding their intricacies and impact. This study investigates senior citizens' perceptions and barriers to healthcare programs and services, aiming to comprehensively explore their experiences. The central focus is understanding program effectiveness in meeting diverse needs, improving the quality of life, and promoting independence. Specifically, this study is dedicated to exploring the following questions:

1. What are the healthcare programs and services for senior citizens?
2. What challenges do senior citizens encounter in accessing healthcare programs and services?
3. What is senior citizens' perception of the healthcare programs and services on their overall wellbeing?
4. What enhancement programs can be proposed to remove the barriers in healthcare programs and services for senior citizens?

METHODOLOGY

Employing a descriptive study approach, the researchers aimed to explore the experiences and perspectives of participants, particularly focusing on viewpoints and barriers related to health programs and services for seniors aged 60 years and above. The study targeted a sample size of 10 participants, comprising five (5) males and five (5) females, all aged 60 years and above, with access to the healthcare center in Barangay Payatas B, Quezon City, Philippines.

Purposive sampling was utilized, and semi-structured, open-ended interviews were the primary data collection instruments. Participants were engaged during the monthly senior citizens' day organized by the healthcare center and through home visits, ensuring a comprehensive understanding from both attendees of organized events and those who might not attend. Guided questionnaires for the semi-structured interviews were designed to be flexible in wording and question order, facilitating shared control over the interview process. These questionnaires were translated into both English and Filipino to ensure accurate understanding.

Formal consent was obtained from Barangay Payatas B officials and the Payatas B Health Center, and signed consent forms were secured from participants before conducting interviews, ensuring ethical compliance and participant willingness. This

methodology aimed to provide a thorough understanding of the perceptions and barriers faced by senior citizens in accessing healthcare programs and services in Barangay Payatas B, Quezon City, Philippines.

RESULTS

The study involved ten senior citizens aged 60 and above from Payatas B, Quezon City. The demographic profile included age, gender, religion, and current work or hobbies, while participants' names were excluded. Interviews were conducted in Filipino, as all participants are fluent in Filipino or Tagalog. The collected data were coded, categorized, and organized into themes addressing the research questions.

Healthcare Programs and Services for Senior Citizens

Table 1 presents the programs and services available to senior citizens. These are healthcare services for existing health conditions, particularly chronic diseases such as hypertension and diabetes. Healthcare services include free medications, laboratory, and consultations. Another is health promotion and wellness. Such programs are focused on physical activities and health education. While there is a high appreciation for existing programs and services, there is also a demand for more responsive services, such as home visits, for more access and responsive supplies of commodities to prevent stockouts.

Table 1. Healthcare Programs and Services

Themes	Sub-themes
Healthcare services for existing health conditions	Free consultations and medications
	Registration of senior citizens for sustainable care and treatment
Health promotion and wellness programs	Physical activities for wellness
	Health education for increased compliance with care
Demand for responsive services	Demand for more home visits and community extension services
	Demand for responsive medicine supplies

Healthcare services for existing health conditions. The senior citizens in Payatas B, Quezon City, are aware of and engage with healthcare services like free medications, health check-ups, and dental care, though accessibility and efficiency vary. Most participants use free services from the barangay health center, though awareness of the available services varies. The center offers extensive services, including check-ups, vaccinations, lab tests, health education, TB treatment, and free wheelchairs and dentures. However, not all seniors utilize or are aware of all services. One participant described the services for the senior citizen population: *"As far as I know, the services*

available at the center include free medication, free vaccines, anti-flu shots, and laboratory services." Another participant shared, *"I receive my free medication for high blood pressure... Losartan. And they also check my blood sugar."*

Most participants also underscored the presence of treatment services aimed at addressing the healthcare needs of senior citizens within the community, especially those with maintenance medications. These services include medicine consultation, regular health screenings, preventive care initiatives, and free common medicines for elderly patients, such as losartan, metformin, and amlodipine. One of the participants highlighted the issue of insufficient services, stating, *"when they don't have the medicine I need, like certain antibiotics, they give me a prescription, and then I buy it outside."*

All participants shared mechanisms to ensure that the service providers properly monitor all senior citizens' health needs. This is done through an established system of recording and registering senior citizens in the barangay health center registry. One participant elaborated on collecting their personal data, stating, *"...we have to show an index card when going to the health center, where my vaccine schedule and record are placed."* Furthermore, they explained the necessity of the index card for scheduling appointments, mentioning, *"...when scheduling an appointment at the center, the index card is needed to register."*

Health promotion and wellness programs. Participants highlighted various health programs and services in Payatas that comprehensively address the community's healthcare needs, particularly for senior citizens. These services include health promotion, screening, and treatment initiatives. Initially, participants emphasized programs that inform and educate seniors, promoting active participation in wellness activities like Zumba classes and health education sessions. These initiatives were praised for empowering seniors to take charge of their health and fostering community engagement. The participants emphasized the importance of health education and activities. *"...we also have Zumba in the barangay every Saturday, but I don't often go,"* shared by one participant. Additionally, they highlighted the value of teaching about health when receiving medication. One participant shared, *"When they give me medicine, they tell me what it's for and what I should avoid."* During visits to the health center, participants routinely received health education alongside their medical care. In addition to prescribing medication, doctors also provide patients with guidance on managing their condition and following their treatment plan. The participants highlighted the valuable health education provided by healthcare professionals, stating, *"...when the physician at the facility prescribes medication, they provide instructions on when to take it, its purpose, and advise on dietary restrictions due to my diabetes and hypertension."*

Health promotion efforts enable the participants to increase their health-seeking behavior. Most participants emphasized the importance of health screening services, which are vital for the early identification and prevention of diseases. These services include X-rays, medical check-ups, and laboratory tests, each serving a distinct role in promoting overall health and well-being. The participants demonstrated awareness of the available services

offered by the health center. One participant said, “I know they also have X-ray and laboratory services, but I haven’t tried them yet.”

Each participant underscored the importance of adhering to a monthly schedule, which allows them to receive free medication and medical check-ups at the health center. The participants provided insights into the process of claiming needed medications, stating, “*The schedule at the center is monthly, usually at the beginning of the month, to get more medicine.*” Additionally, they mentioned the quantity of medication provided, sharing, “*The medicine they gave me is 30 pieces, just enough for one month.*”

Demand for responsive services. Challenges include physical distance from facilities, service consistency, and long waiting times, which can deter usage. Personalized care for immobile seniors is lacking. Suggestions for improvement include comprehensive screenings, better medication management, and expanded outreach to remote or homebound individuals. While healthcare programs are in place, continuous evaluation and adaptation are needed to meet seniors' needs.

Many participants advocate for expanding healthcare initiatives specifically targeted toward this demographic. They propose that health centers organize medical missions or implement additional programs tailored to senior citizens' unique healthcare needs. Moreover, participants emphasize the importance of ensuring an adequate supply of medication for senior citizens. They also suggest conducting medical missions for individuals residing in remote areas who may face challenges in accessing healthcare facilities. The participants suggested advocating more for reaching out to those who live far away and ensuring medication availability. One participant emphasized, “*I know someone who lives far from the health center and has difficulty walking, so they can’t go there. They should do house-to-house visits instead in such cases.*” Another participant expressed, “*I hope they always have a complete stock of medicines and vitamins and that... they never run out because that’s important.*”

Challenges Encounter in Accessing Healthcare Programs and Services

Table 2 shows the challenges experienced by senior citizens in health programs and service delivery. Two themes emerged from the findings. First are the identified barriers to quality healthcare, which were focused on lacking human resources, long waiting times in queues, no services available while scheduled, and access issues related to the distance of residences to the facility. The second concerns their choices as influenced by existing sociocultural practices in their families and the community. These influences include switching preferences or opting for a combination of medical and traditional.

Table 2. Challenges Encountered

Themes	Sub-themes
Identified barriers to quality healthcare	Lacks health human resource
	Long waits in queue
	No services are provided while it is scheduled

	Distance of household to the health center
Choices influenced by socio-cultural practices	Switching to traditional practices for perceived better outcomes
	Opting for mixed of medical and traditional treatments

Identified barriers to quality healthcare. Based on the participants' feedback, it is evident that their experiences varied significantly. While some participants reported events going smoothly without encountering any issues, others recounted facing challenges due to a lack of assistance from the staff. Participants who reported smooth participation most likely received adequate assistance and guidance, allowing them to navigate the event easily. However, most participants shared that staff availability, particularly healthcare providers, is one of the reasons why they have to wait longer in the queue to get their needed service. Health stations are often manned by community health workers and a lean staff of licensed healthcare providers such as doctors and nurses. While community health workers can provide health education and assist the nurses and doctors, doctors and nurses are limited in number due to staffing concerns. Likewise, they rotate in the schedule on different facilities in the area. The participants can see community health workers with very limited capacity to provide care as unresponsive to provide care. One participant shared, *"There's no other reason. It's just laziness for some people because I'm here in line by five o'clock, so I get attended to too quickly."* On the contrary, some participants who frequently visit the health station and understand the situation do not find it an issue. One participant stated, *"I always come here. (You don't have any problems coming here?) No, not at all."*

Another perceived challenge is waiting longer to get the services they came for. Some participants reported difficulties due to a lack of prompt assistance from staff, highlighting shortcomings in the event's support. These participants have encountered difficulties due to a lack of timely assistance and may have felt frustrated and disadvantaged, affecting their overall experience and satisfaction. One participant expressed their struggles in using the services of the healthcare center, *"It's been a while; I've been here since earlier (morning), and I'm still here."* Most participants encountered the challenge of waiting in long, disorganized lines until midday despite the heat. This problem is caused by ineffective queue management strategies or logistical flaws, resulting in frustration and discomfort among most participants. Prolonged exposure to adverse weather conditions also causes feelings of discomfort and impatience, affecting the overall participant experience. Some participants shared their opinions on the system of the healthcare center, *"The line at the center is always long,"* said one participant, and *"Senior citizens keep coming back to the health center,"* said another. At the same time, they wait for their turn in the queue.

On the other hand, some participants shared their dismay at visiting the health center for a scheduled health service just to be informed to come again another day. *"At times, the staff forget the schedule. People come, only to be told to return another time,"* shared one participant.

This difference in experiences emphasizes the subjective nature of individual encounters and the importance of providing adequate support to all participants, implying variations in the quality and availability of assistance provided by event personnel. It also emphasizes considering diverse needs and capabilities when organizing similar activities to ensure inclusivity and accessibility for everyone involved.

Equally important to note are the experiences of those who reside far from health centers. Most participants noted that senior citizens face accessibility issues, prompting some nurses or healthcare workers to make house-to-house visits. However, some participants were skeptical about the quality of care received at home compared to the health center. Along with the common challenge regarding the location of the health center, one participant shared, *“Yes. There are many of us (seniors) here. Mostly elderly people. That’s why the nurses here do house-to-house. If I can, I can still walk. I prefer to visit the health center for a better-quality service.”*

Choices influenced by socio-cultural practices. The majority of the participants engage in cultural practices such as *“hilot”* (traditional massage) and *“tawas”* (ritualistic cleansing with alum), demonstrating the community's reliance on traditional beliefs. Some participants do not adhere to these cultural traditions and prefer alternative approaches. While some people may prioritize traditional healing methods first, others may choose to go straight to the doctor or rely on conventional medicine. Some participants said that they go for traditional means when they perceive that treatment they get from the health center is not helping, *“Sometimes, when you don’t immediately get better at the center, it helps alleviate the condition,”* shared one participant. On the contrary, one participant highlights the importance of medical consultations rather than traditional treatment: *“I don’t really have any beliefs because I go straight here [to the Health Center], just like my grandchild. When they have a cough, they get checked by a doctor. It’s available, and it’s fine.”* Some participants identified a cultural mindset to treat and cure infirmity as common among those raised in the provinces. One participant insisted that they only seek medical care because they weren’t raised in the province, *“I rely on doctors only. I wasn’t raised in the province.”* In addition, a subset of people believe that exercise is effective as a treatment for certain ailments, demonstrating the diversity of perspectives within cultural health practices. The participant emphasizes that exercise is one of the keys to a healthy body. *“Just exercise. Just by my own effort.”*

Senior Citizens' Perception of the Healthcare Programs and Services

Table 3. Perception on the Healthcare Programs

Themes	Sub-themes
Satisfaction with free services	
Dissatisfaction with facility and services	Discomfort due to the physical setup
	Displeasure of a long waiting time
	Disapproval of unpleasant staff
	Dissatisfaction with stockouts of commodities

Expressed understanding of government-provided services	
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Table 3 presents the perception of senior citizens regarding access to health programs and services in Payatas, Quezon City. Three major themes emerged from the findings – satisfaction with free services, dissatisfaction with facility and services, and expressed understanding of government-provided services. Along with dissatisfaction with facility and services, four sub-themes generally describe their experiences. These are discomfort due to the physical setup, displeasure of a long waiting time, disapproval of unpleasant staff, and dissatisfaction with stockouts of commodities like medications.

Satisfaction with free services. Most participants expressed satisfaction with the health programs and services they receive in Payatas, Quezon City, primarily because they are free. Free services include consultations, laboratory examinations, and commodities such as vitamins, vaccines, and medications. The participants likewise enjoy opportunities for health education and participation in medical missions organized for them. One participant described their experience as they were provided with medications after the consultations. While another described it as efficient, describing the effectiveness of the programs as very good due to the availability of medications and the smooth flow of services, “...they do provide free medicines outright after the consultations.”

While most participants are dissatisfied due to the long waiting time, they appreciate the small group learning sessions conducted by community health workers. The participants also highlighted the importance of health education, noting, “Like with health... they explain what the medicine is for because I also like to ask questions,” said one participant. Additionally, they appreciate being informed about dietary restrictions when taking medication, stating, “They inform you about what foods to avoid when taking the medicine.”

Dissatisfaction with facility and services. Based on the ratings provided by most of the senior citizens on a scale of 1 to 5, the effectiveness of the healthcare center's programs and services varies significantly. One senior citizen rated the services as a 1, expressing dissatisfaction with long wait times, staff approachability, medication availability, and discomfort in the waiting area. The participant expressed dissatisfaction: “The service is not good; it’s very hot, and the line is long”, shared one participant, “...sometimes the staff are so rude...” another participant added.

The raised concern on the discomfort due to the physical aspects of the health center becomes more problematic during summer when the temperature rises very high. The health center has no air-conditioning, and despite it being well-ventilated, the cramped long lines exacerbate the condition.

The senior citizens’ day is scheduled for the month's first day. Given the situation wherein all elderly constituency needing medical attention would crowd the health center in one single day every month. While the first day of the month is intended for senior citizens, the health center remains open to the public with other health concerns, which leads to

cramping up and longer queues, hence, longer waiting times for almost all. In most cases, despite the large number of patients waiting, only one physician is available. One participant shared, “...it takes so long because there is only one doctor. Why don't they add more?” While some participants have a clear understanding of the health center's situation as a public facility. One participant shared that they often reassure each other and tell them to be patient while waiting in the queue, “Just be patient because we are dealing with the government, and besides, patience leads to rewards.” Lastly, there are instances when prescribed medications are unavailable in the health centers. In situations like this, senior citizen patients are advised to purchase it from commercial pharmacies. Free medications remain available until the supply lasts.

Expressed understanding of government-provided services. Most of the opinions senior citizens express are rooted in their firsthand experiences at the healthcare center. Some seniors mentioned the need for patience, acknowledging that the services are government-funded and provided free of charge. Public health centers cater to the needs of all, especially the marginalized and the poor. Hence, it is often the best option for most people, not only senior citizens – which often leads to overcrowding of patients, stockouts of supplies, and too few personnel to attend to all.

Proposed Measures for Enhancement of Healthcare Program by Senior Citizens

The findings present two overarching themes as proposed measures by the participants. First is improving access through outreach activities and second is making the facility and services responsive, therefore, senior citizens-friendly.

Improve access through outreach activities. Senior citizens have identified some measures to improve their access to healthcare programs and services in Patayas, Quezon City. A multifaceted approach is proposed to address these challenges. First is improving the physical accessibility of healthcare facilities. Many seniors in remote areas advocate for facilities closer to them, reducing the travel time to access medications. One specific recommendation was having a regular outreach wherein services are brought to their areas. Outreach programs and medical missions are also recommended to ensure inclusivity in healthcare programs, expanding access for many seniors who may otherwise struggle to reach health centers. One participant shared, “Yes, it is far because the travel will need to use a tricycle, there should be an outreach...” Transportation costs are an additional financial burden for senior citizens. Those who chose not to commute complained about the perceived risks of strenuous walking, especially those with contraindicated health conditions. Another participant shared about always worrying about their hypertension when walking back and forth to the health center from their residence, “...just like that, I am anxious because I get too tired, so my BP is high”.

Make the facility and services senior citizens-friendly. Suggestions include adding more chairs to ensure that senior citizens with Musculoskeletal concerns and other health problems can be properly rested and accommodated before their consultations. Other suggestions include implementing programs such as milk and food feeding programs for seniors. In addition, some seniors have expressed concerns about encountering rude and

unapproachable staff. Hence, they also proposed to train the staff to be more sensitive and responsive to their overall clientele. One shared about the unapproachable staff, noting, "...overall the staff is friendly, but sometimes we encounter rude staff." Another participant added, "There are times that the staff are unapproachable."

In addition, while some seniors report no specific barriers to accessing healthcare, others mention challenges such as long waiting times and difficulty scheduling appointments. These are attributed to the absence of medical professionals when needed, which can lead to untreated conditions, exacerbation of chronic diseases, and a sense of neglect among the senior population. The participants also highlighted logistical challenges, expressing, "The scheduling process takes a long time, and the queue is long." Additionally, they expressed concerns about the availability of medical professionals, stating, "Sometimes there is no doctor if needed". Hence, improving staffing is also being proposed to ensure responsive services.

DISCUSSION

This qualitative study investigates the perceptions and barriers to healthcare services among ten senior citizens (5), five males and (5), five females aged 60 and above in Barangay Payatas, Quezon City. The study highlights the awareness among senior citizens regarding available healthcare services, including free medications, health check-ups, and dental care. However, challenges such as physical distance from health facilities, inconsistent service availability, and long waiting times can hinder the full utilization of these services. There's a notable need for personalized care, especially for immobile seniors, suggesting improvements like comprehensive health screenings and expanded outreach programs. Local healthcare facilities, particularly barangay health centers, are crucial in meeting community healthcare needs, offering a range of free services. Mechanisms such as index cards are in place to monitor seniors' health needs. In this study, existing guidelines were referenced, and multiple agencies were involved in providing services for senior citizens. However, only 25% of the 16 health centers conducted comprehensive geriatric assessment (CGA) without an existing health information system (HIS) specifically for senior citizens (González-López et al., 2022).

Participants appreciate the various health programs available, emphasizing a comprehensive approach to healthcare delivery. Recommendations for improvement include expanding outreach programs and ensuring an adequate medication supply. While UHC represents a significant step in improving healthcare access in the Philippines, challenges such as fragmented health information systems and resource shortages persist. The proposed pilot program offers a promising solution by leveraging partnerships and innovative financing models to expand access to UHC and enhance healthcare delivery for underserved populations. Overall, the study provides valuable insights for enhancing healthcare provisions and promoting senior citizens' well-being in the community. (Philanthropy Asia Alliance, 2023)

The experiences of senior citizen individuals varied significantly, with some encountering smooth participation in events due to helpful staff assistance, while others faced challenges and frustrations due to inadequate support. Long, disorganized queues and waiting times, especially in adverse weather conditions, emerged as a significant issue for most participants, likely stemming from ineffective queue management or logistical issues. Moreover, there was a disparity in perceptions regarding the extent and nature of senior citizens' challenges, highlighting the need for further research to effectively understand and address their diverse needs. Furthermore, participants' engagement in cultural practices like traditional massage and ritualistic cleansing showcased the community's reliance on traditional beliefs. However, preferences varied among individuals, with some favoring alternative approaches or conventional medicine over traditional healing methods.

To enhance satisfaction, the healthcare center should prioritize areas for improvement identified by seniors, including wait times, staff approachability, medication availability, and transportation support. Addressing these issues can improve the overall quality of care and ensure that cultural beliefs and preferences are respected and integrated into healthcare interventions.

The inclination towards traditional healing practices such as "*hilot*" (massage) and "*tawas*" (divination ritual) is evident among seniors, with some utilizing these methods before formal medical treatment. Mental health concerns, including stigma and cognitive impairment, are briefly acknowledged, hinting at the potential need for further examination and educational initiatives in this area.

Senior citizens have identified various barriers within healthcare programs and services, proposing measures to address them. A primary concern is the physical accessibility of healthcare facilities, particularly for those residing in remote areas. Suggestions include establishing facilities closer to these communities to reduce travel time and ensure inclusivity through outreach programs and medical missions. Concerns have also been raised regarding encounters with staff perceived as rude or unapproachable, highlighting the significant impact of staff demeanor on the overall healthcare experience for seniors. Suggestions for improvement include increasing seating capacity, implementing feeding programs, and establishing additional centers to cater to those living far from existing facilities.

Despite these challenges, seniors' satisfaction with healthcare programs varies. While many commend the kindness and quality of care healthcare professionals provide, concerns persist regarding service efficiency and responsiveness, highlighting areas needing enhancement.

This section proposes measures to address the challenges faced by seniors and improve healthcare services. First, this section recommends expanding healthcare centers or establishing additional facilities to accommodate more seniors, directly addressing issues such as long waiting times and inconsistent availability. The National Economic and Development Authority (2021) emphasizes expanding healthcare infrastructure and implementing digital health solutions to enhance service delivery.

Outreach programs and medical missions are also suggested to bring healthcare services closer to remote areas, ensuring inclusivity and accessibility for all seniors. Mohd Rosnu, Singh, Ludin, Ishak, Rahman, and Shahar (2022) highlight the importance of removing geographical barriers and enhancing healthcare access for seniors. Ensuring a consistent and adequate supply of medications and vitamins can prevent shortages and promote seniors' health, directly addressing the challenges identified in the study.

Additionally, this section highlights the need to improve staff attitudes and increase sensitivity to seniors' needs, enhancing the overall quality of care. This involves providing training initiatives and resources to cultivate a constructive and positive environment. Lastly, providing educational sessions for seniors can empower them to take charge of their health, understand their treatment plans, and make informed decisions, including guidance on medication usage, dietary restrictions, and lifestyle modifications.

Conclusions

The study provides context on how senior citizens perceive healthcare programs and services in Barangay Payatas B, Quezon City. While most participants are aware of and participate in programs like free medications and health screenings, they face challenges such as long wait times, medication shortages, and limited doctor availability.

To improve, health centers need to offer personalized care, better access to services, and expand outreach to remote areas. Clearer health education and respecting traditional beliefs are also essential. Addressing these aspects will enhance healthcare experiences and outcomes for seniors, create a supportive environment, and establish a foundation for a healthier, more resilient community, benefiting future generations and ensuring long-term stability in Barangay Payatas B.

Additionally, the study underscores the importance of regular monitoring and evaluation of healthcare programs to ensure they meet the evolving needs of senior citizens. By implementing feedback mechanisms and involving senior citizens in the planning and decision-making processes, healthcare providers can create more responsive and effective services. Collaborations with non-governmental organizations and community groups can further enhance resource allocation and service delivery. Overall, a comprehensive and inclusive approach is crucial for improving the quality of life for senior citizens in Barangay Payatas B.

Recommendations

Leveraging this study's findings can provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges, perceptions, and needs of senior citizens within the healthcare system. Utilizing this study as a foundation can significantly save valuable time on data-gathering efforts, allowing researchers to focus more on analyzing and building upon the insights already obtained. Additionally, the following critical information encompasses recommendations for selecting study participants and suggestions for future research.

A. Age Selection of Study Participants:

The study concentrated on senior citizens, with a total of ten (10) participants chosen, comprising five (5) males and five (5) females, all aged 60 years old and above. This deliberate age selection aimed to ensure representation of the target demographic and capture diverse perspectives. As recommended, particular attention was given to including individuals who had recently turned 60 and may not yet be aware of the availability of healthcare programs and services. However, during the recruitment process, it was encountered that some participants who had recently turned 60 were unaware of the services and programs offered at the healthcare center. Consequently, interviews with these individuals could not be conducted, highlighting a potential area for further exploration and targeted outreach efforts in future research endeavors.

B. Locale:

The study primarily targets senior citizens residing in Barangay Payatas B, Quezon City. Notably, the Payatas area comprises three barangays under the local government jurisdiction, namely Payatas A, B, and C. Future researcher endeavors are recommended to explore diverse barangays within the Payatas area to enhance the breadth of geographical representation. This expansion would offer a broader scope of location, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of senior citizens' healthcare needs and experience different community settings.

C. Existing Literature

The studies reviewed in the existing literature provide valuable insights into diverse aspects of senior healthcare, encompassing national-level initiatives, regional disparities, and access challenges specific to the Filipino context. While each study enhances understanding of seniors' well-being, they are constrained by factors such as narrow focus, limited sample sizes, and reliance on qualitative methods, potentially limiting their broader applicability. Recommendations include integrating quantitative methodologies, broadening sample sizes and geographic scopes, and incorporating varied stakeholder perspectives to enrich the depth and relevance of findings. Addressing these limitations can facilitate a more comprehensive understanding of senior healthcare needs and guide targeted interventions to enhance access and outcomes for older adults.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Several ethical considerations were prioritized before conducting the research to protect the rights and well-being of senior citizens participating in the study. Firstly, the research team consulted with the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Barangay Payatas B to ensure compliance and obtain the necessary formal documents. This was done in collaboration with the local health center, allowing the research team to proceed with the study. This collaborative effort ensured that the study design aligned with ethical standards, providing clarity, understanding, and respect for the perspectives and cultural diversity of the participants.

The study emphasizes that participants in Barangay Payatas B will be informed about the study's purpose, benefits, risks, and methodology in both English and Filipino to ensure clarity and understanding. They will also be made aware of their right to withdraw at any time without consequences, guaranteeing that their participation is voluntary and their autonomy is respected.

In data collection, interviews were the primary instrument used in the study. Informed consent was obtained before continuing with the interviews to uphold privacy and confidentiality empathetically and sensitively, avoiding causing distress and ensuring that participants felt comfortable and respected. The researchers carefully designed and validated the questions to address sensitive issues while maintaining a supportive atmosphere.

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